

Wild Remedies: Ethnozoological Practices Among Traditional Healers Of Dima Hasao District, Assam, Northeastern India.

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Ethnozoology focuses on the utilization of animals and their parts in the preparation of traditional medicines. The traditional or folk medicine formulation has been practiced for ages among various tribes and communities worldwide. The study investigates the use of diverse animals and their parts for treating various diseases and ailments by traditional healers in the Dima Hasao district of Assam, India. Conducted over a 12-month period from June 2022 to June 2023, 37 species have been identified which are being utilized by local traditional healers. These species include 18 mammals, 4 reptiles, 3 birds, 5 insects, 1 crustacean, 1 amphibian, 1 mollusc, 1 annelid, and 3 freshwater fishes. Among these animals, 10 globally threatened (IUCN) species were also recorded. The study also lists the products, the mode of administration and the nature of ailments addressed. While the study highlights the vast traditional knowledge within the healer community, it also raises concerns about the use of threatened animals in traditional healing procedures. As a response, the study suggests awareness campaigns and educational programs to enable sustainable practice among the traditional healers, aiming to preserve both biodiversity and traditional knowledge.

Keywords: Ethnozoology, traditional healers, Dima Hasao, sustainable, biodiversity.